

Near-Real-Time 6G Service Operation Enabled by Distributed Intelligence and In-Band Telemetry

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The combination of highly dynamic network services requiring stringent Quality of Service (QoS), especially in terms of end-to-end (e2e) delay, together with capital and operational cost reduction cannot be faced using centralized Software-Defined Networking (SDN) solutions only. In particular, such expected dynamicity requires autonomous near-real-time operation fed with pervasive telemetry to make per-service decisions that ensure the committed QoS, while reducing overprovisioning as much as possible. In this paper, we propose a distributed control architecture based on Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) to assist the SDN controller in the control of network services near-real-time. Per-traffic flow telemetry data is collected from the packet nodes, distributed through the agents in the control plane, and analyzed to assure performance and to anticipate any degradation. Measurements feed flow agents, which are based on Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) models, to make routing decisions aiming at ensuring flow performance. In case that QoS degradation is detected, we propose algorithms to analyze its cause, which can be as a result of some bottleneck in the network. We show how the latter is detected and additional capacity is requested to the SDN controller, which in turn creates an optical bypass to provide additional capacity. The proposed solution is demonstrated experimentally on a federated test bed connecting UPC and CNIT premises. Focused first on the control plane, the feasibility of the proposed architecture and workflows is experimentally assessed. After that, the performance of the near-real-time operation is evaluated at the data plane to verify that the maximum e2e delay is not exceeded for multiple flows, showing the effectiveness of predictive QoS evaluation together with infrastructure and service reconfiguration.

1. INTRODUCTION

The sixth generation (6G) of mobile networks will impose strict requirements not only to the radio segment but also to the transport network, which nowadays is designed to provide constant capacity between locations [1]. In particular, it is expected that the fixed packet and optical network [2] need to provide support to highly dynamic services requiring not only high capacity, but also low delay [3,4]. Huge efforts have been made to develop Software-Defined Networking (SDN) centralized control solutions (see, e.g., [5]), since they have the potential to greatly reduce operational expenditures (OpEx) for network operators. These solutions provide end-to-end (e2e) multilayer network control and can integrate Machine Learning (ML) solutions for many use cases [6], including intent-based networking [7] to assure the required Quality of Service (QoS) and fault management [8,9]. However, providing support to highly dynamic services while assuring their QoS in an efficient and cost-effective way can be only achieved if the transport network is operated autonomously, e.g., based on ML solutions fed with network telemetry [10].

The *e2e delay* is one of the most important QoS metrics to be guaranteed [11]. The delay that packets experience along a route from ingress to egress includes three main components:

queuing delay, *transmission delay* and *processing delay*. Transmission and processing delays are mostly predictable, while queuing delay depends on the instantaneous traffic load (i.e., burst of packets arriving at an output interface), which is difficult to predict. Overprovisioning packet link capacity can minimize queuing delay by reducing the load of output interfaces, but it also increases the Capital Expenditures (CapEx). Such overprovisioning increases with traffic dynamicity, because a low-dynamic lifecycle management based on centralized provisioning and reconfiguration phases cannot follow changes in the network traffic in the seconds scale. In fact, such near-real-time decision making can be hardly implemented in a centralized SDN-based element because of the time it takes to: (1) collect telemetry data from the data plane; (2) convey them to the centralized location; (3) analyze the data; (4) make decisions; and (5) program the data plane. In fact, this results in control loops that introduce significant delay and bring scalability issues to both the control plane network and the SDN control system [12].

In this paper, we extend our previous work in [13,14] and propose a distributed control architecture based on multi-agent systems (MAS) [15] to assist the SDN controller to locally digest large amounts of telemetry data and make near-real-time decisions. The aim is to use the resources allocated by the SDN

controller more efficiently to guarantee the desired QoS performance, e.g., in terms of e2e delay, for connectivity services. Specifically, in this paper, we focus on flow routing and target optimizing resource utilization, while keeping the e2e delay under a maximum tolerated value.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the state-of-the-art related to network telemetry and ML solutions for network automation, especially those based on Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) [16] and MAS, and details the contributions of our work. Section 3 provides an overview of the autonomous flow routing problem and details the proposed distributed architecture. Next, in Section 4, models and algorithms are defined and detailed for the main phases of the lifecycle of packet connectivity services. Armed with such tools, Section 5 defines the workflows for the considered phases of the lifecycle. The discussion is supported by both numerical results and experiments presented in Section 6. Finally, Section 7 draws the main conclusions of this work.

2. RELATED WORK AND CONTRIBUTIONS

Near-real-time autonomous operation is a special type of network automation that requires the availability of new technologies and architectures to be developed in the control and data planes to perform decisions in the seconds scale. One of the required technologies is that of pervasive in-band network telemetry (INT). INT enables the collection of accurate measurements of relevant metrics, including QoS and network state [17,18]. Recent progress on hierarchical telemetry architectures have shown the potential of telemetry collectors implemented in P4 switches in the data plane to aggregate data and simplify data collection in support of decision making [19].

Regarding the application of ML for autonomous network operation, several works in the literature have proposed solutions based on DRL. For instance, the authors in [20] proposed the application of DRL for provisioning connectivity services with delay constraints and guaranteed capacity. Although the routing decisions are made at provisioning time, a similar solution can be used for network reconfiguration. The authors in [21] use multiple DRL agents for multidomain path selection. The authors in [22] proposed DRL approaches for the control of optical connections after the provisioning phase paving the way for a distributed control of connectivity services. Another work exploring the performance of distributed control solutions is [23], where the authors face the operation of optical point-to-multipoint systems. They show that distributed approaches can achieve similar performance to the centralized one, while greatly reducing communication needs in near-real-time scenarios. Using a DRL approach for network operation requires a careful design of the management lifecycle of the DRL models, which should include their initial training using generic traffic before the operation starts, and their fine-tuning during operation. The authors in [24] presented a solution for the related packet flow capacity problem showing the effectiveness of pre-trained models.

Looking specifically to routing at the packet layer, authors in

[25] use DRL techniques to route connection requests by selecting a single e2e path given a selection of candidate paths. In packet networks, *multi-path* routing introduces flexibility in the design and operation of the network by allowing operators to split traffic demands into multiple streams that are routed independently of each other to the destination [26]. A possible routing policy is to evenly split each traffic flow among all available routes. However, such a strategy might fail under dynamic network conditions that can generate congestion in some routes and consequently, lead to the flows QoS degradation. Moreover, routes might have different utilization costs, and hence, the percentage of traffic sent through each route is a complex decision that needs to be dynamically tuned in order to meet robust QoS performance with overall minimum cost. In view of that, the authors in [27] proposed using a MAS for flow routing, aiming at bringing intelligence closer to the data plane to reduce response times. *Node agents* ensure QoS of traffic flows by applying routing policies based on the measured e2e packet delay. They showed a combination of DRL and MAS able to ensure e2e delay and greatly reduced routing costs in dynamic scenarios without previous knowledge of the traffic profile or the background traffic in the network.

In this paper, we consider the operation of several flows between common ingress and egress nodes and massively rely on INT techniques [19] to coordinate their operation. We also exploit the capabilities of a Machine Learning Function Orchestrator (MLFO) [8]: *i*) to manage MAS pipelines, including the deployment of the flow agents (MAS Pipeline Manager); and *ii*) to supervise the flow agents, as well as training DRL models for the agents (multi-flow MAS supervisor). As in [27], we assume that traffic flows are splittable, i.e., they consist of a large number of sub-flows that can be routed independently without incurring penalties derived from packet reordering. The objective is then to find the flow routing policy that balances the incoming traffic of the flows among the available paths, to ensure per-flow QoS (specifically e2e delay). Such a routing policy varies as a function of the incoming traffic of the flow and the network conditions, i.e., the traffic of the rest of the traffic flows in the network. Therefore, the routing policy decision making process is continuously carried out based on the incoming traffic and the e2e measurements that allow the evaluation of the quality of the

Table 1. Summary of components

Component	Short description
<i>MAS Pipeline Manager</i>	Part of the MLFO in charge of the deployment and reconfiguration of MAS agents, their connectivity etc. (see [28] for details)
<i>Multi-flow MAS supervisor</i>	Part of the MLFO in charge of supervising flow agents and training DRL models for the agents in a MAS.
<i>Multi-flow agent</i>	Part of the MAS that collects traffic measurements and includes the flow agents that make dynamic decisions for the flow under control.
<i>Telemetry agent</i>	Part of the MAS that collects (per-flow and aggregated) measures of e2e delay and jitter.

process. Table 1 provides a short description of the main components. Specifically, the contributions of this paper are:

- The control architecture proposed in Section 3 extends that from our previous work in [13,14] to support reconfiguration of resources considering a multi-flow scenario. Two novel components are proposed in this paper: *i*) the multi-flow MAS supervisor in the MLFO; and *ii*) the manager in the multi-flow agent that elaborates periodic reports on the flows' performance.
- Section 4 proposes models and algorithms for provisioning, near-real time operation and resource reconfiguration. Two novel algorithms are defined in this paper: *i*) an algorithm to find the set of routes that can be used by the flow agents; and *ii*) algorithms to analyze the received telemetry data and to analyze the performance of the flows.
- The workflows executed during flow provisioning, near-real time operation, and resource reconfiguration are described in depth in Section 5 and details of the information exchanged in some key messages are provided. Contributions include workflows for: *i*) flow provisioning; and *ii*) for resource reconfiguration during flow operation.

Experimental assessment of the proposed distributed solution has been carried out on a distributed federated testbed connecting the CNIT/SSSA (ARNO testbed) in Pisa (Italy) and the UPC testbed in Barcelona (Spain). This includes the coordination among flow agents making near-real-time flow routing decisions of different flows.

3. AUTONOMOUS FLOW ROUTING OPERATION

The proposed autonomous flow routing architecture is presented in Figure 1a. At the control plane, an SDN controller is in charge of the network; specifically, during flow provisioning, the SDN controller computes a set of allowable routes P_i for every flow f_i , i.e., those that can potentially meet

the required QoS in terms of predictable delay components only. We assume that every individual flow $f_i \in F$ has a particular maximum e2e delay (d_i^{max}) that needs to be satisfied. Figure 1a shows two packet switches that are ingress (R1) and egress (R5) of a set of flows F_{1-5} . Static routing policies may not provide the needed flexibility under dynamic traffic conditions, so its application could result in delays above the maximum for the flow in the case of congestion. In view of that, once each flow is established, the SDN controller hands over its near-real-time control to a *multi-flow agent*, running on top of ingress node R1. The multi-flow agent implements *flow agents* that are deployed by the MLFO, where a specific *multi-flow MAS supervisor* oversees their performance and can tune their parameters and models. Each individual *flow agent* makes dynamic decisions for the flow under control on the amount of flow traffic to be sent through each of the output interfaces related to the allowable routes (*routing policies*). Flow agents are continuously fed with per-flow traffic measurements collected by the local *node agent* and with telemetry data provided by a *telemetry agent* deployed at the egress packet node R5, which measures (per-flow and aggregated) e2e delay and jitter for each of the allowed routes.

Armed with such telemetry data, intelligent and accurate actions can be performed to meet complex operational objectives like ensuring per-flow maximum e2e delay with overall minimum routing cost. For illustrative purposes, Figure 1b shows a small 5-node network, a set of flows F_{1-5} with common ingress and egress nodes R1 and R5 (in general, R1 and R5 do not need to be in the border of the network), as well as other flows (R1-R3 and R2-R5) on the network (*background traffic*). In the example, for every f_i , the SDN controller computes two routes through the packet network: *i*) route R1-R2-R5 ($p1$); and *ii*) R1-R3-R4-R5 ($p2$), which can be used at any time. The SDN controller assigns different costs to each

Figure 1: Proposed architecture for autonomous multi-flow routing (a) and illustrative scenario (b).

Figure 2: Flow control and network resource management.

route (e.g., as a function of the number of hops), so as to give priority to traffic routing.

Figure 2 details the workflow of autonomous multi-flow routing operation, where every flow agent defines routing policies independently. The destination node R5 collects INT data and reports those records to the collector in the telemetry agent (step 1 in Figure 2). Then, per-flow telemetry data is managed by individual processors (step 2) and sent to the multi-flow agent manager in the ingress (step 3). The manager sends telemetry data, local traffic measurements and some other parameters to the specific flow agent (step 4). Each flow agent computes the routing policies to be enforced next for traffic flow f_i (step 5) and, the manager eventually forwards the policies to the node agent that translates them into actions in the packet node (e.g., routing table updates) (step 6).

In our implementation, the flow agents are based on DRL, so routing policies are decided by DRL models. At the flow provisioning time, the multi-flow MAS supervisor selects the most appropriate model for operation from a pre-trained models data base (DB) [24]. Models in the DB are pre-trained in a sandbox domain and classified by their characteristics, such as d^{max} and number of routes available. Because the flow agents are network topology agnostic, pre-training can be performed on a sample network to obtain a general model that operates within the specified characteristics. A complete DB can then be built by considering various d^{max} requirements and total routes. In consequence, the multi-flow MAS supervisor needs to know d^{max} and the number of routes available for each flow to select the model that best fit them and send it to the flow agent to immediately start flow operation.

Once in operation, the flow agent selects the most appropriate action and measures the resulting QoS. Note that the QoS of each flow f_i depends on its input traffic and routing policies, as well as on that of other flows in the network that use common network resources, e.g., flows R1-R3 and R2-R5 in Figure 1b. Therefore, even though flow agents try to balance the traffic through the allowable routes to meet d^{max} , it might happen that delay constraints cannot be met for all the flows during some time periods because of congestion in some intermediate packet node. For that reason, the connectivity of R1 and R5 can be increased by adding additional connectivity that increase the current capacity. In particular, we can consider a multi-layer scenario [1] so, in

case of congestion, R1 and R5 can be connected using an *optical bypass*, i.e., a (virtual) link in the packet network that is supported by an optical connection, which can be activated on-demand.

In the architecture in Figure 2, the manager provides periodical updates on the performance of the flow agents in meeting the QoS requirements of each flow (step I in Figure 2). In case that difficulties are predicted, the multi-flow MAS supervisor in the MLFO requests the SDN controller to add more resources, e.g., increase the capacity of the existing routes or add additional ones (II). The SDN controller manages the resources in the network and, depending on the capacity that is requested, it can decide to establish and activate an optical bypass connecting R1 and R5 (III). Once the optical bypass is available, the multi-flow MAS supervisor advertises its activation. In addition, the flow agent may require new models to properly operate with a different number of routes, so the MAS supervisor provides pre-trained models for the flow agents to operate (IV). The manager in the multi-flow agent distributes the models to the related agents (V).

However, network reconfiguration, particularly the activation of an optical bypass, takes time, e.g., 1 min, and this time might result in a QoS degradation of the flows. Another issue is that, once the bypass is activated, it could be used by other flows in $F_{1,5}$ without any additional cost, which might result in excessive delay if large amount of traffic uses the bypass. For this reason, if the objective is to allow the use of the bypass for flow routing only when it is strictly needed to meet the flow QoS requirements, then the use of the bypass needs to be somehow penalized, so the SDN controller assigns its use with a cost higher than that of routes $p1$ and $p2$. All these together impose the need of some coordination among the flow agents. In consequence, algorithms are required at both, the multi-flow agent manager and the multi-flow MAS supervisor, which is in charge of managing the network resources allocated for the flows $F_{1,5}$. To that end, the multi-flow MAS supervisor receives collected e2e telemetry data that includes the QoS of the flows and the load of the routes together with the aggregated total traffic. After analysis, if the need for additional network resources is identified, it coordinates with the SDN controller via the MLFO and informs the flow agents about the availability of new routes.

4. MODELS AND ALGORITHMS

This section describes the key models and algorithms involved in the proposed autonomous multi-flow routing operation, specifically during: *i) flow provisioning phase*, where the SDN controller finds resources that will support the packet flow; *ii) near-real time operation*, managed by flow agents that ensure the committed QoS, and *iii) resource reconfiguration*, where the load manager operation ensures the availability of just enough network resources to guarantee the committed QoS. Table 2 summarizes the used notation.

Table 2. Notation

Flow provisioning	
G	Graph $G(N, E)$ representing the network topology. N is the set of nodes and E is the set of links.
d^{max}	maximum delay (QoS) to guarantee for traffic flow f .
x^{max}	maximum expected traffic for traffic flow f .
p^{max}	maximum number of allowed routes for traffic flow f .
q^{min}	minimum queuing delay introduced by any route
F	set of flows between a pair of source and target (s, t) nodes. f denotes an individual flow.
P	set of routes computed between (s, t) . p denotes an individual route.
Near-real time operation	
$s(t)$	state at time t
$x(t)$	amount of input traffic at time t .
k_p	allowed capacity of route p .
c_p	cost of route p .
$a_p(t)$	percentage of input traffic to be routed through route p at time t
$y_p(t)$	amount of traffic directed through route p at time t .
$r(t)$	reward at time t .
$r_{delay}(t)$	reward by the measured delay
$r_{cost}(t)$	reward by routing cost
α_{delay}	Constants for reward components
α_{cost}	
β	penalty when the maximum delay is exceeded
β	penalty when the maximum delay is exceeded
Resource reconfiguration	
$P(f)$	set of routes for flow f .
ℓ_{fp}	maximum normalized load measured along any interface of path p of flow f .
Z	summary of current and predicted values of traffic, load, and e2e delay.

Algorithm 1. Route computation algorithm**INPUT:** $G=\{V,E\}$, $req=<s, t, x^{max}, d^{max}, p^{max}>$, τ **OUTPUT:** P

```

1:  $G_{aux} \leftarrow G$ 
2: for each  $e \in G_{aux}$ .E do
3:   if  $e.cap < \tau \cdot x^{max}$  then  $G_{aux}.E.pop(e)$ 
4:  $P \leftarrow k\text{-SP}(G_{aux}, s, t)$ 
5: for each  $p \in P$  do
6:    $p.d^{min} \leftarrow transmDelay(p) + q^{min}$ 
7:   if  $p.d^{min} > d^{max}$  then  $P.pop(p)$ 
8:  $sort(P, <'d^{min}', 'similarity'>, ASC)$ 
9: return  $P[1..p^{max}]$ 

```

A. Flow provisioning phase

Upon the reception of a new flow provisioning request, req , the SDN controller runs Algorithm 1 to compute the set of allowable routes P for the flow. Algorithm 1 receives the current network state, summarized by graph G , and the flow request including ingress s and egress t nodes, maximum traffic x^{max} and delay d^{max} to be guaranteed, and maximum number of allowed routes p^{max} . In addition, parameter τ specifies the minimum percentage of x^{max} that every individual route has to support. After some initialization (line 1 in Algorithm 1), the algorithm discards those links with

residual capacity below $\tau \cdot x^{max}$ (lines 2-3) and uses the k-shortest path algorithm to compute the routes on the resulting graph (line 4). For each route, the minimum expected delay d^{min} is computed considering its total distance and a minimum value of queuing delay. The expected delay is used to discard those routes that cannot meet d^{max} (lines 5-7). Finally, the remaining routes are sorted by multiple criteria, like cost and capacity (line 8) and returned (line 9). The complexity of the is related to that of computing k-shortest paths, e.g., using Yen's algorithm [29], which is $O(k \cdot |N| \cdot (|E| + |N| \log |N|))$.

B. Near-real time operation

The flow routing agents are based on DRL and thus, include: *i)* an *DRL agent* in charge of learning the best actions to be taken based on the current routing state and the received reward; and *ii)* an *environment* that computes the state and a reward for the action taken. As in our previous work in [27], from the various DRL methods available in the literature, we rely on Twin Delayed Deep Deterministic Policy Gradients (TD3) for the flow agents [16]. TD3 is an off-policy DRL technique employing a dual set of *critic* Deep Neural Networks (DNN) alongside with an *actor* DNN, which is updated with a certain delay. We denote the ensemble of critic and actor DNNs operating within the DRL framework as the *model*, which is responsible for dynamically determining the best routing policy for the flow.

The formulation of the DRL model is as follows:

$$s(t) = x(t) \cdot \frac{\sum_{p \in P} k_p}{|P|} \quad (1)$$

$$y_p(t) = a_p(t) \cdot x(t) \quad (2)$$

$$r(t) = \alpha_{delay} \cdot r_{delay}(t) + \alpha_{cost} \cdot r_{cost}(t) \quad (3)$$

$$r_{delay}(t) = \begin{cases} -\beta - \frac{d(t)}{dmax}, & d(t) > dmax \\ 0, & d(t) \leq dmax \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$r_{cost}(t) = -x(t) \cdot \sum_{p \in P} a_p(t) \cdot \frac{c_p}{k_p} \quad (5)$$

We define the state $s(t) \in \mathbb{R}^+$ as the input traffic $x(t)$ scaled by the average capacity of the available routes P , where k_p represents the capacity of route $p \in P$ (eq. (1)). Every element in action $a(t) \in [0, 1]^{|P|}$ specifies the proportion of input traffic to route through route p , and thus $a(t)$ represents the routing policy to be applied. Then, the amount of traffic directed through route p is $y_p(t)$, defined in eq. (2). The reward function $r(t)$ aims to penalize actions that lead to poor QoS or increased network cost. Consequently, the multi-objective reward function in eq. (3) considers a reward based on the measured e2e delay (r_{delay}), as well as on the routing cost (r_{cost}); constants α_{delay} and α_{cost} weight each reward component. The r_{delay} component is defined in eq. (4), where β is a predetermined penalty applied when the maximum delay is exceeded. Finally, the r_{cost} component (eq. (5)) computes the cost of the distribution of traffic on the routes, based on the cost (c_p) and the capacity of each route.

Algorithm 2. Telemetry Data Analysis

INPUT: $\omega = \langle x_{fp}, \ell_{fp}, d_{fp}, a_{fp} \rangle, \forall f \in F, p \in P(f), t$
OUTPUT: Z

```

1: DB.update( $\omega, t$ )
2:  $Z \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3: for each  $f \in F$  do
4:    $Y \leftarrow \text{select}(DB, "d_f", [t-w, t])$ 
5:    $d_{cur} \leftarrow Y[w]$ 
6:    $d_{pred} \leftarrow \text{forecast}(Y, t+m)$ 
7:    $x \leftarrow \emptyset; \ell \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
8:   for each  $p \in P(f)$  do
9:      $Y \leftarrow \text{select}(DB, "x_{fp}", [t-w, t])$ 
10:     $x_{cur}(p) \leftarrow Y[w]$ 
11:     $x_{pred}(p) \leftarrow \text{forecast}(Y, t+m)$ 
12:     $Y \leftarrow \text{select}(DB, "\pi_{fp}", [t-w, t])$ 
13:     $\ell_{cur}(p) \leftarrow Y[w]$ 
14:     $\ell_{pred}(p) \leftarrow \text{forecast}(Y, t+m)$ 
15:    $Z(f) \leftarrow \langle d_{cur}, d_{pred}, x_{cur}, x_{pred}, \ell_{cur}, \ell_{pred} \rangle$ 
16: return  $Z$ 

```

When the flow agents are deployed, they are configured with a pre-trained model able to tackle the uncertainty of input traffic [27]. Then, the manager in the multi-flow agent collects measurements of the flow traffic $x(t)$ from the local node agent and e2e delay $d(t)$ from the telemetry agent and sends them to the specific flow routing agent for flow f_i (see Figure 2). The measurements are received by the flow agent environment that computes the current state $s(t)$ and reward $r(t)$ and sends them to the DRL agent to determine the best action $a(t)$. The action is sent to the manager who is in charge of sending the routing policies to the local node agent.

C. Resource reconfiguration

The operation of the flow agents needs to be continuously monitored and analyzed to prevent degradations in the performance of the flows. To that end, telemetry data is first analyzed at the multi-flow agent and a summary is sent to the multi-flow MAS supervisor for flow performance analysis.

Algorithm 2 shows the telemetry data analysis that is performed at time t , when a data sample ω is received. The sample contains the current routing policies a_{fp} that are configured in the local node, together with three features measured for every flow f and path p from the local and the telemetry agents: *i*) the traffic count x_{fp} , *ii*) the maximum load ℓ_{fp} computed as the maximum normalized load measured along any interface of the path; and *iii*) the e2e delay d_{fp} . The purpose of the telemetry data analysis is to return the summary Z that contains the current and predicted values of each of the aforementioned telemetry features. In particular, predictions aim at providing estimation of the features at time $t+m$, being m sufficiently large to include both the time needed by MAS supervisor to carry out some performance evaluation, as well as for the SDN controller to implement some resource reconfiguration (e.g., optical bypass activation) in response to multi-flow MAS supervisor notifications. The multi-flow MAS supervisor uses Z for several purposes apart of flow performance evaluation, such as model tuning and retraining.

Algorithm 2 starts updating its internal database DB with

Algorithm 3. Flow Performance Analysis

INPUT: $Z, d_{high}, \ell_{low}, \ell_{high}$
OUTPUT: W

```

1:  $W \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2: for each  $f \in F$  do
3:    $\langle d_{cur}, d_{pred}, \ell_{cur}, \ell_{pred} \rangle \leftarrow Z(f)$ 
4:   if  $\max(d_{cur}, d_{pred}) < d_{high}$  then continue
5:   if  $\min(\ell_{cur}, \ell_{pred}) < \ell_{high}$  then
6:      $W \leftarrow W \cup \langle f, \text{"model_reconf"} \rangle$ 
7:   else for each  $p \in P(f)$  do
8:      $\ell' = \max(\ell_{cur}(p), \ell_{pred}(p))$ 
9:     if  $\ell' > \ell_{high}$  then
10:       $\Delta k \leftarrow k_p \cdot (\ell' - \ell_{low}) / \ell_{low}$ 
11:       $W \leftarrow W \cup \langle f, p, \text{"cap_inc"}, \Delta k \rangle$ 
12: return  $W$ 

```

the received telemetry data sample ω (line 1). Then, after initializing the summary data Z , the algorithm performs delay forecasting per flow using the last w aggregated delay measurements in the DB and estimating the expected delay at time $t+m$ using polynomial extrapolation (lines 2-6). In particular, the i -th degree polynomial that maximizes the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) is chosen as predictor [30]. A similar procedure is used to estimate traffic and load, but independently for each path of a flow (lines 7-14). Finally, current and predicted values are populated in the summary data Z and returned (lines 15-16). The complexity of the algorithm is $O(k^*|F|)$.

Algorithm 3 in the multi-flow MAS supervisor receives the data summary Z generated by the telemetry data analysis process at every time t . The purpose of this algorithm is to return a diagnosis set W with a list of notifications related to the flows performance. The method follows a threshold-based approach where the received current and predicted features are compared against reference thresholds for delay (d_{high}) and load (ℓ_{low}, ℓ_{high}). After initializing the diagnosis set W (line 1 in Algorithm 3), every flow is processed independently (lines 2-11). Delay and load features for the current flow are extracted from Z (line 3). Without loss of generality, we consider that if both current and predicted delay are under the threshold d_{high} , flow performance is good, i.e., flow agent is performing as expected (line 4). Otherwise, delay is (or will be) high and hence, some actions must be taken to mitigate such performance degradation. Two performance degradation causes can be distinguished: *i*) if the minimum load of the flow is below ℓ_{high} , we assume that the model running in the multi-flow agent is not taking advantage of unused capacity and, therefore, a model reconfiguration for that flow should be triggered (lines 5-6); and *ii*) if the load is high, additional capacity might be needed (lines 7-11). In such case, capacity increment Δk is requested for each path whose load exceeds ℓ_{high} , in order to make its load equal to ℓ_{low} . Such additional capacity is computed with respect to the allowed capacity k_p of the evaluated path. The complete diagnosis set is eventually returned (line 12), which will be processed by the MAS supervisor to trigger model reconfiguration and/or request additional capacity to the SDN controller.

Figure 3: WF1: Flow provisioning.

5. DESCRIPTION OF THE WORKFLOWS

This section describes in depth the workflows executed during: *i*) flow provisioning (WF1); *ii*) near-real time operation (WF2); and *iii*) resource reconfiguration (WF3). We assume the scenario in Figure 1b.

A. Flow provisioning phase

Recall that the information needed for flow provisioning includes the ingress and egress nodes, as well as the maximum traffic and delay to be guaranteed. The SDN controller uses Algorithm 1 to compute a set of routes and selects a subset of them with enough capacity to meet the maximum traffic of the flow, and configures the routing tables in the nodes in each route, without making any resource reservation for the flow, so as to leave the freedom to operate to the MAS. Then, the MAS pipeline is deployed and configured for near-real-time operation based on the received telemetry that needs to be configured as specified by the MAS. The workflow carried out during flow provisioning is shown in Figure 3. Details of some selected messages for this and the rest of the workflows (identified with the labels in their respective workflow) are presented in Table 3.

The workflow starts after the packet nodes along the routes supporting in the flow (see Subsection 4.A) have been properly configured (step 0 in Figure 3). The SDN controller sends the flow details (message *a*) to the MLFO. Among other information, message *a* includes: *i*) the QoS parameters to be guaranteed for the flow; *ii*) identification of the ingress and egress nodes and ports; *iii*) the node agents for configuration purposes; *iv*) the set of metrics and other capabilities (e.g., periodicity, aggregation, etc.) for telemetry; and *v*) the path list with details of the ports in ingress and egress nodes, including their maximum usable capacity, and their cost. Based on that information, the MAS pipeline manager in the MLFO decides the locations where agents are needed to operate the flow and deploys them together with the necessary connectivity (see [8] for details). The designed solution allows several flows to be controlled between the same ingress and egress nodes, so the MAS pipeline includes the MAS agents, as well as the multi-flow MAS supervisor,

Table 3. Information in selected messages

Msg Id	Information
a (WF1)	Create flow. Flow details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flow Id QoS parameters (d^{max}, x^{max}) Ingress (node/port, agent details) Egress (node/port) INT collector (telemetry capabilities) Route list (path Id, src/dst ports, k_p, c_p)
e (WF1)	Telemetry configuration for ingress node and collector: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MAS agent details (IP, port, endpoint) Metrics to collect Specific configuration (period, aggregation, etc)
1 (WF2)	Traffic telemetry for every flow: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flow Id List of metrics and measured values during the specified period.
5 (WF2)	E2e telemetry for every flow: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flow Id List of metrics and aggregated values during the specified period disaggregated by route.
8 (WF2)	Routing policy for every flow: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flow Id a_p.
10 (WF3)	Required reconfiguration of resources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> List of flow Ids Capacity and delay constraints
13 (WF3)	Reconfiguration of resources for every flow: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Route list (path Id, src/dst ports, k_p, c_p)

which is only deployed if no other flows between those nodes exist (step b). Once the deployment is completed, the MAS pipeline Manager configures the multi-flow MAS Supervisor and provides the configuration received from the SDN controller (message *c*). The multi-flow MAS Supervisor is now in charge of configuring the agents. The configuration includes the DRL model to run in the flow agent and the details of the telemetry that both the flow agent and the telemetry processor will receive (message *d*). Finally, the multi-flow MAS Supervisor sends the selected telemetry configuration to the MAS pipeline manager, which sends it back as a response to the SDN controller (message *e*). The details of message *e* are summarized in Table 3. The SDN controller uses the telemetry configuration to activate the telemetry in the nodes along the paths, as well as in the telemetry collector (message *f*), so the details of the MAS agent (IP address, port, etc.) where the data has to be sent are included in message *e*.

B. Near-real time operation

The workflow for near-real time operation of the traffic flows is outlined in Figure 4. Let us assume that flow routing policies are configured at node R1 (message 0 in Figure 4) to enable multi-path routing. Input flow traffic measurements are collected and sent periodically to the local multi-flow agent for every traffic flow entering in the network through that node (message 1); the messages contain the selected metrics, e.g., packet and bit count for every traffic flow (see

Figure 4: WF2: Near-real-time operation.

Table 3). Packet delay and other metrics are measured along the path and reported through INT messages to the P4 collector (message 2), which performs the aggregations specified in WF1 and computes statistics, e.g., min, average, and max of delay, jitter, and load. Periodically, the P4 collector sends the computed statistics to the collector in the local telemetry agent (message 3). The aggregated QoS telemetry message includes per-path statistics for every flow. The received statistics are then processed by each of the flow processors (message 4) that compute per-flow QoS telemetry measurements and send them to the corresponding flow agent (message 5). When flow QoS statistics are received in the multi-flow agent, the manager pushes both traffic and QoS measurements to the corresponding flow agent (message 6), which uses the current DRL model (see Subsection 4.B) to take an action on the routing for the flow. Routing decisions are gathered by the manager (message 7) who eventually sends them to the P4 switch (message 8). The routing policies in message 8 are defined as the percentages of input traffic to be routed through each of the routes (see Table 3). Internally, the P4 switch translates this policy into flow rules to efficiently perform packet forwarding according to defined percentages.

C. Resource reconfiguration

As defined in Subsection 4.C, the near-real-time operation of the flows between the same ingress and egress is continuously monitored by the manager in the *multi-flow agent* and summarized to the *multi-flow MAS supervisor* in the MLFO

(message 9 in Figure 5). In the case of detection of expected performance degradation due to the lack of networking resources, the *multi-flow MAS supervisor* computes the required capacity that needs to be added, the list of flows that will use it, and other requirements, like delay constraints, and sends a request to the SDN controller (message 10) (see Table 3). The SDN controller decides the action to be taken, e.g., increase the capacity of one of the existing paths or add a new path to the set of allowed paths. In this example, let us assume that the SDN controller decides to create an optical bypass connecting nodes R1 and R5. To that end, the SDN controller coordinates the setup of the new lightpath at the optical layer (message 11) and configures a new virtual link between the nodes and the new path (message 12). Finally, the SDN controller replies to the *multi-flow MAS supervisor*, via the MLFO, with the details of the action taken (message 13). For instance, the availability of a new path (see Table 3). In that case, the *multi-flow MAS supervisor* finds the most appropriate DRL model to operate each of the flows and sends the details of the new path together with the new models for the affected flows to the manager in the *multi-flow agent* (message 14), as well as the details of the new paths to the telemetry agent (message 15). Note that during this whole process, the flows were operated with the models in place and available resources, which were expected to produce performance degradation. In consequence, it is of paramount importance that the detection occurs with as much anticipation as possible to leave time for the new resources and models to be available before such degradation has any impact of the performance of the flows.

6. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we experimentally demonstrate the proposed distributed MAS fed with telemetry measurements to perform near-real time multi-flow operation on a federated testbed. The experimental set up, that reproduces the architecture and scenario depicted in Figure 1, is first described in detail. Next, the algorithms and workflows defined in Sections 4 and 5 are experimentally assessed, and finally, the performance of the proposed near-real time operation is experimentally evaluated.

Figure 5: WF3: Resource reconfiguration during flow operation.

Figure 6: Federated testbed setup for the experiments.

A. Experimental Setup

Figure 6 presents the federated testbed and the experimental deployment, which reproduces a 5-node network scenario similar to that in Figure 1b. The packet- optical network is deployed at the CNIT/SSSA ARNO testbed, whereas the distributed MAS is deployed at UPC premises. Five native in-kernel P4-programmable software switches (P4-NIKSS) are deployed and connected to create the packet network. P4 switches are connected among them using 10G interfaces. P4 switches run on a separate server to maximize performance. Specifically, an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6238R CPU @2.20GHz server with 256GB RAM is used. An additional P4-based software process is deployed as telemetry data collector, which receives INT data from the P4 switches [19].

In order to reproduce network congestion and selectively introduce delay in some of the paths of the traffic flows, a Juniper M10i router equipped with 1G interfaces is connected to switch R1, as depicted in the inner graph in Figure 6. Selected flows are forced to traverse the Juniper router before route switching, thus generating different congestion scenarios. Regarding the optical layer, the optical bypass between R1 and R5 is based on a pre-programmed packet-optical whitebox employing 10G and 100G optical pluggables. The pluggables are connected to an Optical Line System, with three 80km fiber spans and line optical amplifiers, by means of an arrayed waveguide gratings multiplexer. The optical connection between the two pluggables is established and enforced locally by OpenConfig-enabled SDN agents co-located with the SONiC node operating system. Finally, a Spirent SPT N4U equipped with 10G ports is used as packet generator for two different traffic flows ($f1$ and $f2$), both from R1 to R5. In our case, flows are identified by source and destination IP. For validation purposes, the Spirent tool is also used as flow traffic sink. In the experiments, R1 measures per-flow traffic entering the switch, before being forwarded through the different paths. In particular, three alternative paths are considered: $p1$ (R1-R2-

R5), $p2$ (R1-R3-R4-R5), and $p3$ (R1-R5, using the optical bypass active on demand).

As illustrated in Figure 2, the distributed system consists of several interconnected software components. Specifically, the *telemetry agent*, which is part of the distributed telemetry architecture [10], includes: *i*) a telemetry collector that periodically receives telemetry data from the P4 collector; and *ii*) a per-flow telemetry processor. In addition, *flow agents* running inside the *multi-flow agent* make routing decisions for each traffic flow. In this case, the multi-flow agent at R1 includes flow agents for both $f1$ and $f2$. REST API interfaces have been implemented between agents and P4 systems. MAS agents and the MLFO, including all the components and interfaces have been implemented in Python 3.10.4 and run inside Docker containers. Three separated virtual machines (VM) for the agents and the MLFO, with Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS as operating system, have been deployed to emulate a distributed environment.

B. Experimental assessment of the workflows

This section is devoted to the experimental demonstration of the workflows defined in Section 5: *i*) flow provisioning (WF1); *ii*) near-real time operation (WF2); and *iii*) resource reconfiguration (WF3). The captures in this section use the labels for the exchanges messages as defined in the related workflow in Section 5. The information in most of the messages (see Table 3) is encoded as a JSON object. Note that messages exchanged between functional blocks in the same system, e.g., inside the multi-flow agent, are not captured.

WF1 is triggered after a new flow request has arrived to the SDN controller in the control plane, which has run its provisioning procedure to properly configure the nodes in the data plane. Figure 7 presents the exchanged HTTP messages captured with Wireshark (see WF1 in Figure 3 for details). The SDN controller sends a request to the MLFO to deploy and configure the MAS in charge of near-real time control of that flow (message *a*). Figure 7 shows the details of message *a* that includes the id of the flow, the QoS parameters for the flow, the details of the ingress and egress nodes and the list of paths that can be used for the flow ($p1$ and $p2$). Once the agents are deployed in the selected locations, the MLFO deploys a multi-flow MAS supervisor for the new MAS, which uses the received information to create descriptors to configure the multi-flow agent collocated with R1 and the telemetry agent collocated with the P4 collector (messages *d*). Finally, the MLFO replies the SDN controller (*e*); the details of message *e* are shown in Figure 7, which include the reference of the agents for the P4 agents of R1 and collector to communicate with them, the metrics to be collected from the nodes and the configuration, which includes the collection period and the activation of data aggregation for that period. The SDN controller configures the agents in the P4 nodes supporting the flow, as well the P4 collector and activate the telemetry with the received configuration (*f*) and WF2 for near real time flow routing operation starts.

Figure 7: WF1: Capture and details of messages.

Figure 8: WF2: Capture and details of messages.

Figure 9: WF3: Capture and details of messages.

Figure 8 presents the capture of the HTTP messages exchanged during the first iteration in WF2 (see WF2 in Figure 4 for details). The configuration of flow agent includes the initial routing policy that is applied when the flow operation starts (message 0); new policies will be defined based on the subsequent measurements. Traffic volume is measured by the agent in the ingress P4 node and sent to the manager in the multi-flow agent (1). The details of message 1 are presented in Figure 8 and include the counters of packets and bytes for the flow. The P4 collector receives and aggregates INT measurements for the flow and sends them to

the collector in the telemetry agent (3), which processes them and sends to the manager in the multi-flow agent (5). Message 5 includes measurements per path of the required QoS parameters (delay, jitter and load in our case) during the collection period (see Figure 8). The manager, takes both, traffic and e2e measurements and sends them to the flow agent for decision making. The new routing policy is then sent to the ingress P4 node agent (8). An example of routing policy in message 8 is shown in Figure 8, where the traffic of the flow is routed evenly on the available paths *p1* and *p2*.

WF2 continues and policies are computed based on the

received measurements. The operation of this flow and other flows between the same ingress and egress nodes is continuously overseen by a common multi-flow MAS supervisor in the MLFO (message 9 in Figure 9). In the case that degradation because of lack of capacity is anticipated, more resources need to be added and WF3 formally starts to reconfigure the involved flows (see WF3 in Figure 5 for details). In such case, the multi-flow MAS supervisor sends a request to the SDN controller specifying the required increment of capacity and delay constraints of such capacity (10); see the details of message 10 in Figure 9. In the experiments, the SDN controller decides to create an optical bypass connecting R1 and R5 directly, and the controller configures the virtual link in the two P4 switches (12). Once the optical bypass is configured, the SDN controller informs the MLFO (13) and includes the list of flows and the paths that can be used for their operation (see Figure 9). Finally, the MLFO updates the configuration of both the multi-flow and the telemetry agents (14-15). The new configuration entails deploying new models for the agents so they can make routing decisions on three paths.

C. Performance evaluation

The performance of the proposed near-real time operation was evaluated on the federated testbed in Figure 6. The Spirent packet generator was configured to reproduce traffic for flows $f1$ and $f2$, while paths $p1$ and $p2$ through the packet network were initially available for supporting the flows. Additional traffic was generated between R3 and R4 with a constant pattern very close to 10Gb/s, which made that routing traffic

through $p2$ resulted in very high delay, which in practice forced to use $p1$ only. The e2e delay was measured by the Spirent connected at R5. Figure 10a (up) shows the traffic generated (48 hours) for flows $f1$ and $f2$, as well as the aggregated traffic ($f1+f2$). The traffic was intentionally generated with the aim to generate daily variation with different peaks, being the highest one at 16h with values close to 1Gb/s, which is the capacity of the interfaces in the Juniper router. Note that the traffic of the individual flows follows a clearer and sharper periodic pattern than the aggregated one, that presents more differences between consecutive days.

In order to illustrate the proposed near-real-time operation, we setup a maximum delay to be assured (d^{max}) for the agents to make the appropriate flow routing actions. To this end, we conducted a preliminary test where optical bypass is never active. Figure 10a (down) shows the obtained e2e delay for both flows with a very high peak due to congestion in the input interface to the Juniper router. Note also that the e2e delay is under 0.6ms (with some variation) during the rest of the analyzed period. In consequence, we configured $d^{max} = 0.6$ ms during flow deployment in WF1.

Figure 10b presents the obtained results when the architecture proposed in Section 3 was deployed and d^{max} is set to 0.6ms. Figure 10b (up) shows the aggregated traffic ($f1+f2$) and through the packet network ($p1+p2$) and through the optical bypass ($p3$) when it is active. We observe that only $f1$ used the optical bypass, whereas $f2$ was always routed through the packet network. Figure 10b (down) presents the obtained delay, where we observe that d^{max} was

Figure 10: Experimental measurements. Flows use the packet network only (a); the optical bypass is used to reduce delay (b).

never exceeded. In addition, during the periods of high traffic, the optical bypass was activated since the flow supervisor anticipated the possibility of excessive delay. It is worth noting that during the second traffic peak, at around 42h, the bypass was activated although the e2e delay did not exceed d^{max} . This was as a result of the anticipation for the prediction in Algorithm 2 (parameter m). Such anticipation needs be configured as a trade-off of the risk of providing episodes with excessive delay (if m is short) and the risk of activating the optical bypass unnecessarily (if m is long).

7. CONCLUDING REMARKS

A distributed control architecture based on MAS to assist the SDN controller to make autonomous near-real-time decisions for QoS assessment has been proposed and experimentally assessed. In particular, autonomous flow routing was demonstrated focused on ensuring e2e delay.

Flow operation was modeled with three workflows for flow provisioning, near-real-time operation, and resource reconfiguration. During flow provisioning, the SDN controller selects available network resources for the flow and coordinates with the MLFO to deploy a MAS pipeline in charge of its near-real-time control. The proposed solution considers coordination among multiple traffic between the same ingress and egress nodes, which can share resources in the network. During flow operation, DRL-based flow agents make near-real-time routing actions to provide the required performance with the minimum cost based on the collected telemetry. A multi-flow MAS supervisor was proposed to track the performance of the flow agents. In the case of QoS degradation is anticipated, the required increment of capacity computed and requested to the SDN controller.

The proposed distributed control architecture, algorithms and workflows were experimentally assessed in a federated testbed spanning UPC and CNIT premises. Details of the messages exchanged highlighting the information exchanged. The performance was experimentally evaluated and show that the obtained e2e delay was kept under the maximum. Anticipation of performance degradation was demonstrated which triggered the activation of an optical bypass. This anticipatory activation of the optical bypass underscores the balance between preventing excessive delays and avoiding unnecessary bypass activation which may increase both capital and operational costs of the network.

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